

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D2.3 Turbine-Receiver Interconnection Tubing

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SUMMARY	<p>The deliverable D2.3 of the project POLYPHEM is a set of air ducts and valves which constitutes the interconnection between the power block and the solar receiver. It is planned in the framework of the Work Package 2. The document describes the technical specifications of these sub-components.</p> <p>The content of this deliverable fully complies with the Grant Agreement number 764048 signed between the beneficiaries and the European Commission. It also complies with the project Consortium Agreement signed by the beneficiaries. This deliverable cannot replace the role neither of the Grant Agreement nor of the Consortium Agreement, which are evidence for the project.</p>
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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

FULL TITLE	SMALL-SCALE SOLAR THERMAL COMBINED-CYCLE
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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and a Rankine organic cycle machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

A prototype plant of 60 kW_{el} with a thermal storage of 1300 kWh is designed, built and installed on the site of the experimental solar tower of Themis in Targassonne (France). The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnologicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
M	Month
MS	Milestone
ORC	Orcan Energy GmbH or Organic Rankine Cycle
PU	Public
PICC	Power Induced Catalytic Combustor (IP property of KAEFER)
WP	Work Package

1. DEMONSTRATOR FOR WP2.3 (TURBINE-RECEIVER INTERCONNECTION TUBING)

1.1 TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION AND DESIGN PARAMETER

The Interconnection tubing connects the gas turbine with the solar receiver and the combustor (PICC).

The choice of pipe diameters, valves and bends has significant impact on the pressure losses within the air circuit and finally the power output of the turbine. Moreover, the choice of materials for the tubing on the hot side (downstream receiver/ combustor) must respect temperatures of up to 800°C. Furthermore, pipes and valves must not be oversized in order to avoid resonances in large volumes and improved dynamic behaviour.

Based on the turbine parameters and expected pipe lengths pressure loss calculations have been carried out considering both, the flow from the compressor to the turbine as well as the flow from the heat source to the turbine. The results of this calculation are shown in Figure 1. Following pipe diameters have been chosen respecting a maximum pressure loss of 10 mbar per tube:

- compressor to heat source: DN150
- heat source to turbine: DN200

Figure 1: pressure losses in air circuit

Figure 2 shows the valve that was purchased to switch between solar and fuel operation.

The valve combines following properties:

- organic shape to avoid turbulences
- available with electric drive (to avoid pressurized air connection)
- available in DN 150 size
- special sealing to stand temperatures of 190°C

Figure 2: Valve for switching between solar/ fuel operation

After design freeze of the machine room (exact location of receiver, power-block and combustor) an isometric drawing will be created which will be the basis of the tender for the tubing.